

Supplementary material

A. Vietnam's Country Context

A.1 Overview

Vietnam's current energy landscape relies heavily on fossil energies [1,2], as seen in Figure A.1. With a 97 million population and USD 366 billion in Gross Domestic Products (GDP), Vietnam utilised 95 million tons of oil equivalent (MTOE) of total primary energy supply (TPES) and 66 MTOE of total final energy consumption (TFEC) in 2020 [3,4]. The country reached full electrification by 2016, and three-quarters of Vietnam's energy flows into the industry and transport sector [3,5]. Meanwhile, the energy and carbon intensity were 0.979 MTOE/capita and 2.7 kgCO₂e/capita, respectively [3].

Figure A.1. Sankey diagram of 2020 Vietnam energy systems. Adapted from IEVN (2021)

A.2 Energy System

Coal and oil dominated Vietnam's energy use in 2020 (Figure A.2), particularly since the "Doi Moi" economic reform massively expanded mining and exploration [6]. With indigenous reserves of 3,390 million tons of coal and 460 and 610 million cubic metres of crude oil and natural gas, the country reached its peak net exports in 2007 [7,8]. As the maturing field depleted, the rapid increase in energy demand forced Vietnam to become a net coal and oil importer in 2015 and soon become an LNG-importing nation [2,9]. Rising importation also happened for petroleum products due to restrictions on crude supply [10]. Total imports are currently at 48% of the TPES and are predicted to rise to over 60% by 2035 [3,11].

Figure A.2. Vietnam's TPES and TFEC structure by fuel in 2020. Adapted from IEVN (2021).

Despite its massive wind (650 GW) and solar (380 GW) potential in the power sector, only 29% of the on-grid electricity generation came from renewables in 2020, mainly hydropower [3,12]. Through PDP 8, Vietnam aims to increase this share to 50% by 2030 and up to 75%-80% by 2050 [13].

As the third-largest manufacturer of PV modules, Vietnam experienced a 25-fold solar capacity expansion in 2019 [1,14]. However, this "boom" was then followed by a "bust" cycle due to the curtailment issues associated with Feed-in-Tariffs (FIT) expiration and insufficient grid capacity [15]. Meanwhile, wind power development lagged due to high capital investment and technological readiness, while geothermal and off-grid hydropower potentials remain untapped [16–18].

A.3 Transportation

Transport historically contributed to 25% of Vietnam's TFEC despite the slight drop in 2020 due to COVID-19 travel restrictions [3]. The vested interest in economic growth has massively increased passenger and freight transport activities by five-fold and three-fold since 2000 [15,19,20]. Road vehicles comprise 90% of the transport emissions, resembling their shares in passenger and freight transport (Figure A.3) [21,22].

Figure A.3. Activities for passenger and freight transport in Vietnam (2015-2020). Adapted from IRF [22].

Transport is Vietnam's largest user of oil products, constituting 95% and 65% of the country's gasoline and diesel intake [3]. The unique challenge of two-wheeler domination (Figure A.4) heightens traffic congestion and air pollution issues, particularly in major cities [23,24]. The market share of electric two-wheelers (E2W) in Vietnam is also the highest among Southeast Asian nations [24]. Meanwhile, ethanol production for biofuel only constituted 1% of the total sector consumption [3].

Figure A.4. Market shares of Vietnam’s road vehicle technologies based on vehicle volume (stocks) in 2020. Adapted from IRF [22].

A.4 Key Stated Policies

After proclaiming the Net Zero Emission (NZE) target by 2050, Vietnam updated the NDC and approved the JETP mechanism, which is envisioned to mobilise multi-year financing of USD 15.5 billion to support energy transition [25,26]. Figure A.5 demonstrates that Vietnam’s government had established robust national policy frameworks to substantiate those international targets, including PDP 8, NEMP, and the Action Programme on Green Energy Transition in Transportation.

³ NZE target was announced at the 26th Conference of Parties (COP 26) World Leaders’ Summit in 2021

Figure A.5. Vietnam's stated national policies related to climate mitigation, energy transition, and transport decarbonisation.

Supplementary material B. Reference Energy System

Figure B.1. Vietnam OSeMOSYS Model – Reference Energy Systems.
 Modified from the previous Vietnam CCG model [27].

Supplementary material C. Data

Table C.1. Vietnam baseline transport activities. Adapted from Tan et al. [28].

Activities (in billions)		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Road							
Motorcycle	<i>pkm</i>	99.781	107.948	116.930	123.823	136.404	110.717
Car	<i>pkm</i>	2.759	2.985	3.233	3.424	3.772	3.062
Bus	<i>pkm</i>	2.842	3.075	3.331	3.527	3.885	3.154
Truck	<i>tkm</i>	51.515	57.377	63.459	71.011	78.964	75.163
Railway							
Train	<i>pkm</i>	4.150	3.391	3.658	3.542	3.155	1.509
Freight train	<i>tkm</i>	4.036	3.198	3.617	4.039	3.763	3.819
Inland Waterway							
Ship	<i>pkm</i>	3.065	3.220	3.505	4.500	4.813	5.363
Freight ship	<i>tkm</i>	42.065	45.051	48.609	52.580	55.998	51.630

Table C.2. Socio-economic assumption. Adapted from previous Vietnam studies [3,28,29].

Parameters	Unit	Value	Growth (Description)
Gross Domestic Product	Billion USD	346	2.23% (highly conservative, only manufacturing sector, assumed for freight transport growth)
Population	Million people	97	1.99% (highly conservative, assumed for passenger growth)
Currency conversion rate	USD / VND	0.085	n/a (2019, used for converting cost and analysing documents)
Discount rate	%	10	n/a (previous model assumption)

Table C.3. Emission factor. Adapted from MONRE [30].

Energy Carrier	Emission Factor (<i>kg CO₂e/TJ</i>)
Biomass	100,000
Coal	98,300

Crude oil	73,300
Natural gas	56,100
Gasoline	69,300
Diesel	74,100
LFO	69,300
Biofuel	66,000

Table C.4 Summary of policy targets related to Vietnam transport decarbonisation

No	Targets	Document	Year
Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment (MONRE)			
1	Mitigate the GHG emission from transport (37.5 MtCO ₂ e).	Decree 6/ND-CP	2020
2	Encourage the use of electricity and green energy in transport using E5 gasoline (biofuel).	Decision 888/QD-TTg	2022
3	Increase energy efficiency in transport by applying standards on fuel quality and emissions.	Decision 896/QD-TTg	2022
4	Transitioning freight load from road to inland waterway and railway, passenger from private to public vehicles.		
Ministry of Transport (MOT)			
1	Reduce fuel and oil consumption in transport.	Decision 280/QD-TTg	2019
2	Regulate fuel economy for two-wheelers, cars, and new vehicles.		
3	Promote electric mobility and storage (battery) technology.	Resolution 55/NQ/TW	2020
4	Transport Development and Strategy.	Decision 1095/QD-BGTVT	2021
5	Improve fuel efficiency and accelerate green energy conversion.	Decision 876/QD-TTg	2022

Table C.5. Techno-economic parameters of electricity generation technologies, 2020. Adapted from Allington et al. [29] and EREA and DEA [31].

Technology	Capital Cost	Fixed Cost	Operational Life	Efficiency	Avg. Capacity Factor
<i>Units</i>	<i>[USD/kW]</i>	<i>[USD/kW]</i>	<i>years</i>	-	-
Biomass Power Plant	2,200	49.50	25	0.38	0.7
Coal Power Plant	1,460	39.60	60	0.30	0.75
Geothermal Power Plant	4,700	20.80	50	0.10	0.7
Light Fuel Oil Power Plant	600	10.00	50	0.40	0.25
Oil Fired Gas Turbine (SCGT)	2,500	18.00	50	0.40	0.25
Gas Power Plant (CCGT)	770	36.70	30	0.55	0.55
Gas Power Plant (SCGT)	1,250	24.10	30	0.35	0.55
Solar PV (Utility)	930	15.50	30	1.00	0.23
Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)	2,162	120.00	35	0.33	0.3
Large Hydropower Plant (Dam) (>100MW)	1,500	37.70	40	1.00	0.49
Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW)	800	41.90	40	1.00	0.49
Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW)	5,500	8.32	40	1.00	0.49
Onshore Wind	1,500	42.00	30	1.00	0.15
Offshore Wind	2,150	70.00	30	1.00	0.27
Nuclear Power Plant	1,500	138.00	60	0.33	0.83
Utility-scale PV with storage	1,000	14.80	30	1.00	0.23
Onshore Wind with storage	2,078	42.93	30	1.00	0.147
Light Fuel Oil Standalone Generator (1kW)	2,700	38.00	20	0.42	0.4
Solar PV (Distributed)	2,220	42.62	24	1.00	0.23
Off-grid Hydropower	2,466	64.86	40	1.00	0.48

Table C.6. Summary of techno-economic parameters for transport technology.

Technology	Avg. energy intensity	Avg. fuel economy	Avg. occupancy / load factor	Operational life	Capital Cost	Fixed Cost	Learning Rate (*only for EV)
Passenger	[MJ/pkm]	[L/100km]	[p/vehicle]	[years]	[2015 USD/pkm]	[2015 USD/pkm]	%
Motorcycle	2.7-3.4	2.3-3.3	1.2	10-15	920-1,380	20-27	1.5%
Car	3.3-7.5	4.2-11.4	1.7	12-20	2,097-3,145	47-62	1.4%
Bus	3.0-6.9	4.7-9.1	35	15-20	2,478-3,718	55-74	1.4%
Train (Railway)	1.5-2.6	0.02	130	30-40	3,366-5,050	67-100	1.7%
Ships (Waterway)	2	1	500	25	2,574	51	n/a
Freight	[MJ/tkm]	[L/100km]	[t/vehicle]	[years]	[USD/tkm]	[USD/tkm]	%
Truck	1.2-2.8	0.1	25	10-15	2,755-4,133	82-123	2.5%
Train (Railway)	1.6-2.6	0.01	260	30-40	10,727-16,091	214-321	1.7%
Ships (Waterway)	1	0.04	1000	25	2,730	54	n/a

Figure C.1. Fuel costs projection for imported petroleum products in Vietnam.
Adapted from DEA [32], IEVN [3], PV Oil [33]

Supplementary material D. Supplementary Results

D.1. Additional Sensitivity Analysis Results

D.1.1. Drought impacts

Technical constraints that represent drought in the combined transport scenario (ALL), the model confirms that lower reservoir levels may decrease hydroelectricity output by 5%-15% through the modelling period (Figure D.1). The model responds by resorting to an additional 20% coal and 10% biomass power, which undo the effects of decarbonisation and lead to 1.3 MtCO₂e higher emissions in 2030.

Figure D.1. Reduction in annual hydroelectricity generation between the transport combined strategies (ALL) (upper dots) and the drought simulation (lower dots) results

D.1.2. Refinery expansion impacts

The PDPL scenario presents the need to import 1,386 PJ petroleum products in 2050, two-thirds of which are gasoline as the primary fuel for passenger road transport modes. Figure D.2 illustrates that combining all three low-carbon transport strategies (ALL) will reduce the total imported oil products by 371 MTOE (77%) and pairing it with refinery capacity expansions will alleviate 96% of its total imports by 2050.

Figure D.2. Petroleum fuel importation profile in the baseline scenario (PDPL), the combined transport decarbonisation scenario (ALL), and the results after refinery expansion

However, refineries have been running at sub-optimal capacities and will undergo scheduled maintenance, which may cause the oil import to surge, and dampen the result of this supplementary exercise [10,34,35]. With the assumption of 4.4 billion barrels of crude oil reserve [36], the model does not endogenously calculate the need for imports, whereas in real condition, crude oil imports must be done to fulfil Vietnam’s refinery specifications [3].

D.2. Other Results

D.2.1. Total system emission results

Through the lens of total period system emissions, there are interchanges of emission sources between petroleum-based emissions and coal power plants and biofuel-based emissions in the scenarios (Figure D.3). Figure D.4 further demonstrates how residual emissions after the highest carbon tax level scenario (CT100) differs from the NDC, JETP and NZE scenarios, which is prominent in identifying the hard-to-abate sectors, particularly after 2030. The residue can be linked to coal and biomass heating demand, which must be replaced with natural gas to provide high, stable heat but with less carbon intensity.

Figure D.3. Changes in total accumulative systems emission indicating trade-offs between transport fuel air pollutions and upstream (power sector) emissions

Figure D.4. Residual emission from related energy carriers indicating hard-to-abate sectors

D.2.2. Other sector demand projections

Demand for other service sectors is kept the same in all non-optimised scenarios to isolate the impact of transport decarbonisation strategies. Meanwhile, the unconstrained demand in target-based scenarios demonstrate how decarbonising coal and biomass heating demand in residential and industrial sectors have significant roles beyond the transport decarbonisation strategies in achieving climate ambitions (Figure D.5).

Figure D.5. Comparison of industrial, residential, and commercial sectors' demand profile in optimised scenarios (NDC, JETP, and NZE) and the transport scenario (ALL)

Table D.2. Summary of results – emission per scenario

Year	REF	PPPL	PPDPH	MS	FS	FE	ALL	ALL+PPDPH	NDC	NZE	JETP	ALL+CT5	ALL+CT20	ALL+CT50	ALL+CT75	ALL+CT100	Drought	Ref Expand	Grid Expand	
2015	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771	322771
2016	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641	351641
2017	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046	366046
2018	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903	361903
2019	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916	377916
2020	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370	350370
2021	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048	363048
2022	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885	365885
2023	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669	369669
2024	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656	373656
2025	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973	375973
2026	409875	377834	377834	372847	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845	367845
2027	418668	377101	377101	372699	368240	367275	364686	368710	363030	280300	303634	364686	364686	364686	364686	364686	364686	364686	364686	364686
2028	428763	377123	377123	371979	369600	365561	363172	367434	360290	270290	295846	363172	366786	348898	307614	302148	384732	377833	367833	367833
2029	438225	376442	376442	371283	368769	363738	361623	366039	350281	260281	288058	361623	346976	321344	298312	282897	389446	376613	366613	366613
2030	446838	376635	376635	374593	371640	367342	363026	360334	350271	250271	280271	350126	348101	326454	288321	262869	388322	369133	357940	357940
2031	452803	364444	363435	359297	352065	349535	348541	351170	348840	241261	279126	346751	334883	321194	281904	257198	376012	362454	347447	347447
2032	461772	356719	349443	352521	345266	341339	339629	336735	347410	232251	277982	332702	314575	274168	251982	361825	348112	348112	348112	348112
2033	470566	351793	338805	347275	342082	334919	333611	325184	345980	223241	276837	326549	322084	307156	270079	248186	350068	336441	336441	336441
2034	479227	349947	336315	344611	331456	330706	330706	321597	345490	214231	275693	328682	312951	302744	265622	243730	346299	332629	332629	332629
2035	478287	348817	333549	343257	349162	328887	328887	328340	343119	205221	274548	323365	309849	301572	265239	244898	341710	328900	328900	328900
2036	481094	350444	332703	344900	350112	329339	328563	315977	341889	196212	273404	325878	308100	300615	264304	246941	348326	326776	326776	326776
2037	484364	355239	332664	349523	354666	332569	332215	324190	340258	187202	272259	328239	306515	297156	263446	250093	350093	336030	336030	336030
2038	487559	362573	337655	356688	357690	339442	338253	324159	338828	178192	271115	334234	306056	292858	263404	255046	354775	329810	329810	329810
2039	490705	370246	343316	364261	360422	344461	344546	327159	337398	169192	269970	340527	305577	293252	266105	258483	359909	334171	334171	334171
2040	498632	377926	348979	371821	364455	350601	350573	330819	335967	160172	268826	346786	305622	294845	266012	261905	364387	338493	338493	338493
2041	514123	389012	362509	383727	383931	359736	358074	340713	333107	142153	266537	356074	308625	300815	267315	371331	349247	349247	349247	349247
2042	514123	389012	362509	383727	383931	359736	358074	340713	333107	142153	266537	356074	308625	300815	267315	371331	349247	349247	349247	349247
2043	521466	393858	368156	389385	386339	362918	361296	344716	331676	133143	265392	361296	310414	304294	277783	269667	373867	353436	353436	353436
2044	528855	396290	372727	392740	391026	365574	364048	347536	330246	124133	264248	363980	312183	307670	282027	376383	356493	356493	356493	356493
2045	536212	403345	385600	396759	395351	372143	366549	355401	328816	115123	263010	367261	314161	311461	285699	276157	378868	364993	364993	364993
2046	543822	408345	388265	402431	400120	376983	370365	356280	327385	108113	261959	369496	316791	315340	291627	279680	381638	366400	366400	366400
2047	551128	412471	389618	406445	404001	378179	372615	355792	325955	97104	260814	371388	319259	319259	297364	283296	382077	366057	366057	366057
2048	557887	416513	391011	410319	408652	381040	374838	355815	324255	88094	259670	373315	323493	321708	304027	285679	382485	365619	365619	365619
2049	565051	420443	392162	414196	412456	382914	376762	354984	323094	79084	258525	375218	334097	321765	310684	286991	382798	364941	364941	364941
2050	566071	425482	393908	418976	415301	386052	380338	354706	321664	70074	257381	378460	348049	345041	339057	309436	383836	359143	359143	359143
2051	574178	438954	410004	432130	413360	393640	391668	368528	318447	62366	254807	389350	353752	353160	346395	317863	399207	365317	370704	370704
2052	581836	450269	425207	443407	422041	404772	403143	381526	315263	55506	252259	398245	361654	358818	350294	321827	410375	379802	379802	379802
2053	589579	460047	435791	453029	430543	413770	412400	390467	312110	48400	249736	408932	369785	363937	355414	321135	419750	390721	388178	388178
2054	597616	470326	446067	463143	440470	423085	421948	398732	308989	43966	247239	418007	378441	372584	342808	322608	429624	400749	397722	397722
2055	606293	480771	456803	473716	460950	432839	430130	407379	300599	39130	244767	426280	367288	381441	371345	329920	439763	410727	408472	408472
TOTAL (Mill.)	19.31	15.80	15.25	15.61	15.47	14.94	14.86	14.50	13.90	8.45	11.90	14.79	13.90	13.02	12.90	12.34	15.46	14.77	14.66	14.66
Emission Reduction (Compared to PPDL)																				
2030	70303	-2042	-4995	-9293	-13609	-16301	-23723	-26364	-126364	-96364	-26509	-28534	-28534	-50181	-88314	-113766	11887	-7502	-18695	-18695
2050	140589	-4.5%	-1.3%	-2.5%	-3.0%	-4.3%	-6.3%	-7.0%	-33.6%	-25.6%	-7.0%	-7.6%	-7.6%	-13.3%	-23.4%	-30.2%	3.1%	-2.0%	-5.0%	-5.0%
2050	140589	-31.57%	-6506	-10180	-39430	-45144	-70775	-103617	-355408	-168101	-47021	-77433	-80441	-80441	-116045	-116045	-41646	-66339	-61634	-61634
2050	33.0%	-7.4%	-1.5%	-2.4%	-9.3%	-10.6%	-16.6%	-24.4%	-83.5%	-39.5%	-11.1%	-18.2%	-18.9%	-18.9%	-20.3%	-27.3%	-9.6%	-15.6%	-14.5%	-14.5%

Table D.3. Summary of results – total costs (in million US\$) of the system per scenario

Scenario	Fuel Cost	Fixed Cost	Capital Cost	Variable Cost
PDPH	14.6670	98.0578	612.4610	5.1883
PDPL	15.2560	91.9549	499.2175	5.1266
NDC	11.8845	72.4173	468.3532	4.5888
JETP	9.5445	73.0362	484.3908	4.6583
NZE	9.7378	75.5544	776.9726	5.8570

Table D.4. Summary of results – investments (in million US\$) per scenario

Timeframe	Scenario	Biomass Power Plant	Coal Power Plant	Large Hydropower Plant (>100MW)	Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW)	Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW)	Off-grid Hydropower	Gas Power Plant (CCGT)	Gas Power Plant (SCGT)	Solar PV (Utility)	Utility-scale PV with 2 hour storage	Solar PV (Distributed)	Onshore Wind	Onshore Wind with storage	Offshore Wind
2021-2025	PDP(L/H)	2141	5877	0	0	4367	2476	11515	1688	588	1187	0	16007	312	6450
2026-2030	PDP(L/H)	2138	6519	3068	0	4362	2179	11800	1688	494	998	0	15537	305	6450
2031-2035	PDPL	2060	2681	1594	0	679	4575	572	563	25045	2218	11448	12214	688	34400
	PDPH	2059	1511	1595	0	682	7256	578	563	28336	3506	17120	17655	1059	45956
2036-2040	PDPL	2060	841	1594	0	680	4279	572	563	23265	2053	10746	12903	688	34400
	PDPH	2061	0	1595	0	677	6785	578	563	26321	3245	16067	18342	1057	45956
2041-2045	PDPL	2223	841	7249	936	1086	4251	572	563	22573	1888	10746	12214	688	34400
	PDPH	2222	0	7250	1262	1089	6739	578	563	25396	2984	16067	17655	1059	45956
2046-2050	PDPL	4323	841	5969	1575	976	4237	572	563	20477	1716	10749	11833	674	32960
	PDPH	4323	0	5969	1250	974	6705	578	563	23066	2713	16070	17102	1034	44033

Supplementary material E. Evidence Reviews

Evidence reviews are performed to extract the scenario narratives from publications. This study conducts a qualitative scenario design utilising the Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA) method [37,38] for interpreting and synthesising three strategies for transport decarbonisation in Vietnam. REA, or rapid reviews, is an emerging method in health and science policy research [39–42]. It is less comprehensive than the systematic review, with less time, scope, and inclusion criteria, but still retains the essential technique [38,43]. The method is chosen to allow the involvement of active searching in public databases and the ability to extract a broader narrative, including from grey literature and policy documents [44–46]. The REA quality in this research is limited due to the absence of expert and stakeholder elicitation [47].

Review method: Rapid Evidence Assessment (secondary data, literature review) [39].

Objective: Non-impact questions:

What are the stated decarbonisation policy strategies for the transport and energy sector in Vietnam? What are existing modelling practices in transport decarbonisation?

E.1 Search strategy

Sources

Databases : Google Scholar

Journals : Science Direct, Wiley

Search string

Transport + Decarbonisation + Strategy + Vietnam + Energy + Transition + Modelling

Phrases

“Transport Decarbonisation” / “Emission Reduction” / “Energy Transition”

E.2 Inclusion criteria

Inclusion:

Language: English

Article type: academic and grey literature

Period: January 1st, 2013 - July 31st, 2023

Accessibility: Freely accessible

Title: Include Vietnam as the focus or energy/transport modelling as the method

Findings: scenarios, policies, decarbonisation strategies

Exclusion:

Documents from snowballing

E.3 Number of documents

	<i>Science Direct</i>	<i>Wiley</i>	<i>Google Scholar</i>
<i>Initial search</i>	482	393	1600+
<i>Comprehensive search terms (phrase and keywords)</i>	76	76	201

<i>Exclusion / Inclusion criteria</i>	Date	72	69	180
	Accessibility	70	57	165
	Title	52	44	131
	Findings	48	39	108
<i>Quality Assessment (with consideration of external recommendation)</i>		18	12	37
<i>Final Sample</i>		9	7	15

E.4 List of Final Samples

Table E.1. List of final samples for synthesising the scenario design and narrative.

Transport Strategies	Modelling and Analysis	Energy Transition
1. ERIA (2023) - EV Policies in ASEAN Countries.	12. Briand, et al. (2023) - Passenger transport decarbonization in emerging economies: policy lessons from modelling long-term deep decarbonization pathways.	21. ADB and ADBI (2016) - Vietnam Energy Sector Assessment, Strategy and Roadmap.
2. Emodi et al. (2022) - Transport sector decarbonisation in the Global South: A systematic literature review.	13. Breu et al. (2019) - Exploring an alternative pathway for Vietnam's energy future.	22. Shem et al. (2019) - Potentials and opportunities for low carbon energy transition in Vietnam: A policy analysis.
3. Tran et al. (2022) - Two-wheelers in Vietnam: A baseline analysis of fleet characteristics and fuel consumption.	14. Dixon et al. (2022) - Enabling Environments for E-Mobility and Renewable Energy Integration in Southeast Asia.	23. Arioli et al. (2020) - Transportation strategies for a 1.5 °C world: A comparison of four countries.
4. Lan et al. (2021) - Towards a Carbon Neutral Economy in Vietnam: Modal Shifting in Transportation Sector.	15. EREA and DEA (2021a) - Vietnam Energy Outlook Report 2021.	24. Eeg (2023) - A study of Vietnam's energy transition pathway to low-carbon development.
5. Parker (2021) - A decoupling analysis of transport CO2 emissions from economic growth: Evidence from Vietnam.	16. Nguyen et al. (2018) - A LP I/O model for mapping low-carbon scenarios for Vietnam in 2030.	25. Ha-Duong (2023) - Vietnam's JETP: a background report.
6. Ramachandran (2021) - Emission Reduction Potential of Energy from Biomass Residues in Southeast Asia's Road Transport.	17. Plazas-Niño et al. (2022) - National energy system optimization modelling for decarbonization pathways analysis: A systematic literature review.	26. WB, 2022a - Clean Energy Transition in Vietnam Technical Analysis and Mobilizing Financing.
7. Roy et al. (2021) - Development of on-road emission inventory and evaluation of policy intervention on future emission reduction toward sustainability in Vietnam.	18. Talvela (2022) - Decarbonisation policies in Vietnam - a PLEXOS modelling study on alternative policy scenarios.	27. Neefjes and Nhien (FES) (2021) - Prospects for a Socially Just Energy Transition in Viet Nam: 2021 and beyond.
8. Thao, et al. (2023) - Summary of policies: Transport GHG reduction in view of the Net-Zero Emissions target in Viet Nam.	19. Tan et al. (2022) - Comparing long-term energy pathways in Vietnam (cost optimisation) (OSeMOSYS).	28. Nguyen (2019) - Energy Transition, Poverty and Inequality: Panel Evidence from Vietnam.
9. Trinh and Le (2018) - Biofuels Potential for Transportation Fuels in Vietnam: A Status Quo and SWOT Analysis.	20. Tan et al. (2022) - Power System Flexibility Analysis for Energy Pathways in Vietnam (OSeMOSYS-Flextool).	29. Joshi et al. (2021) - Development of RE Data for Facilitating the Clean Energy Transition in Vietnam.
10. Tuan et al. (2021) - Study of electric mobility development in Viet Nam.		30. Parker, S. (2021) - A decoupling analysis of transport CO2 emissions from economic growth: Evidence from Vietnam.
11. UNESCAP (2021) - Enhancing shift towards Sustainable Freight Transport in Asia Pacific.		31. Roy et al. (2022) - Comprehensive evaluation of electricity generation and emission reduction potential in the power sector using renewable alternatives in Vietnam.

References for Supplementary material

- [1] International Energy Agency (IEA). Southeast Asia Energy Outlook 2022. <https://www.iea.org/reports/southeast-asia-energy-outlook-2022>.
- [2] Shem C, Simsek Y, Hutfilter UF, Urmee T. Potentials and opportunities for low carbon energy transition in Vietnam: A policy analysis. *Energy Policy* 2019;134:110818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.06.026>.
- [3] Institute of Energy Vietnam (IEVN). Vietnam Energy Statistics 2020. Vietnam National Energy Efficiency Programme (VNEEP); 2021.
- [4] World Bank (WB). Vietnam Country Climate and Development Report. The World Bank; 2022.
- [5] Le PV. Energy demand and factor substitution in Vietnam: evidence from two recent enterprise surveys. *Journal of Economic Structures* 2019;8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40008-019-0168-9>.
- [6] Anh NTT, Duc LM, Chieu TD. The evolution of Vietnamese industry. United Nations University World Institute for Development Economics Research; 2014. <https://doi.org/10.35188/unu-wider/2014/797-4>.
- [7] Asian Development Bank (ADB). Pathways to low-carbon development for Viet Nam. Asian Development Bank; 2017.
- [8] Asian Development Bank and Asian Development Bank Institute (ADB and ADBI). Viet Nam: Energy sector assessment, strategy, and road map. 2016.
- [9] PetroVietnam Gas (PV Gas). LNG in PDP 8: from concept to reality. PetroVietnam Gas News 2023. <https://www.pvgas.com.vn/en-us/news/lng-in-pdp-8-from-concept-to-reality> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [10] Hagagy A. Vietnam's Nghi Son refinery may incur \$1 bln loss in 2023 - Kuwaiti document. Reuters 2023.
- [11] Climate Analytics. Decarbonising South and South East Asia: Shifting energy supply in South Asia and South East Asia to non-fossil fuel-based energy systems in line with the Paris Agreement long-term temperature goal and achievement of Sustainable Development Goals. 2019.
- [12] Joshi M, Ranola J, Novacheck J, Sky H, Grue N. Development of Renewable Energy Data for Facilitating the Clean Energy Transition in Vietnam. 2021.
- [13] Vu K. PDP8: Vietnam's \$135 billion power plan for 2030. World Economic Forum 2023. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2023/05/vietnam-pdp8-power-plan-for-2030/> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [14] Broom D. Viet Nam has installed 6 coal plants' worth of solar in a year. World Economic Forum 2021. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/02/viet-nam-solar-power-surge/>.
- [15] Neefjes K, Nhien NTT. Prospects for a Socially Just Energy Transition in Viet Nam: 2021 and beyond Koos Neefjes & Ngo Thi To Nhien. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung (FES); 2021.
- [16] Cuong TT, Le HA, Khai NM, Hung PA, Linh LT, Thanh NV, et al. Renewable energy from biomass surplus resource: potential of power generation from rice straw in Vietnam. *Scientific Reports* 2021;11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-80678-3>.
- [17] Nguyen DL. A critical review on potential and current status of wind energy in Vietnam. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2015;43:440–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.060>.
- [18] Nguyen PA, Abbott M, Nguyen TLT. The development and cost of renewable energy resources in Vietnam. *Utilities Policy* 2019;57:59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2019.01.009>.
- [19] Hue PT, Tuyet NTA. Evaluation of energy intensity of transport service sectors in Vietnam. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 2021;28:11860–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-07652-4>.
- [20] Parker S. A decoupling analysis of transport CO2 emissions from economic growth: Evidence from Vietnam. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation* 2021;16:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2021.1952661>.
- [21] Oh JE, Cordeiro M, Rogers JA, Nguyen K, Bongardt D, Ly TD, et al. Addressing Climate Change in

- Transport Volume 1: Pathway to Low-Carbon Transport. World Bank; 2019.
- [22] International Road Federation (IRF). World Road Statistics. World Road Statistics 2023. <https://worldroadstatistics.org/> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [23] Huu DN, Ngoc VN. Analysis Study of Current Transportation Status in Vietnam's Urban Traffic and the Transition to Electric Two-Wheelers Mobility. *Sustainability* 2021;13:5577. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105577>.
- [24] Tran D-S, Le H, Yang Z. Two-wheelers in Vietnam: A baseline analysis of fleet characteristics and fuel consumption in 2019 and 2020. International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT); 2022.
- [25] Foreign Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO). Vietnam's Just Energy Transition Partnership: political declaration. GOV UK 2022. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/vietnams-just-energy-transition-partnership-political-declaration> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [26] Ha-Duong M. A new North-South climate cooperation mechanism: Just Energy Transitions Partnerships (JETP). CIRED Research Seminar 2023. <https://hal.science/hal-04058057/> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [27] Tan N. Comparing long-term energy pathways in Viet Nam: a simple cost-optimization approach with OSeMOSYS. Zenodo 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317309>.
- [28] Tan N, Ambunda R, Medimorec N, Cortez A, Krapp A, Maxwell E. Transport Starter Data Kit: Viet Nam. Zenodo 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7998248>.
- [29] Allington L, Cannone C, Ioannis Pappis, Karla Cervantes Barron, Usher W, Pye S, et al. Selected 'Starter Kit' energy system modelling data for Vietnam (#CCG). PREPRINT (Version 1). Research Square 2021. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-757746/v1>.
- [30] Socialist Republic of Vietnam Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment (MONRE). Viet Nam Report on National GHG Inventory for 2016. 2020.
- [31] EREA, DEA. Vietnamese Technology Catalogue 2021. 2021.
- [32] Danish Energy Agency (DEA). Fuel Price Projections for Vietnam: Background to Vietnam Energy Outlook 2021. *Ea Energy Analyses*; 2021.
- [33] PetroVietnam Oil (PV Oil). Announcements of price stabilization fund 2023. <https://www.pvoil.com.vn/en-US/announcement-of-price-stabilization-fund> (accessed January 1, 2023).
- [34] Uyen NDT, Cang A, Low E. Vietnam's Top Oil Refinery Cuts Processing on Cash Squeeze. *BloombergCom* 2022.
- [35] Vu K. Vietnam to import additional 2.4 mln cu m of petroleum products in Q2. *Reuters* 2022.
- [36] Tran QM. Projection of fossil fuel demands in Vietnam to 2050 and climate change implications. *Asia & the Pacific Policy Studies* 2019;6:208–21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app5.274>.
- [37] Warren P. Demand-side policy: Global evidence base and implementation patterns. *Energy & Environment* 2018;29:706–31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305x18758486>.
- [38] Warren P. Evidence reviews in energy and climate policy. *Policy Press* 2018;16:83–98. <https://doi.org/10.1332/174426418x15193815413516>.
- [39] Collins A, Coughlin D, Miller J, Kirk S. The Production of Quick Scoping Reviews and Rapid Evidence Assessments: A How to Guide December 2015. 2015.
- [40] Jia J, Axelsson Ka, Chaudhury A, Taylor E. A Rapid Review of GHG Accounting Standards. *Social Science Research Network* 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4523132>.
- [41] UK Civil Service. Rapid Evidence Assessment toolkit index 2014. <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20140402164155/http://www.civilservice.gov.uk/networks/gsr/resources-and-guidance/rapid-evidence-assessment>.
- [42] UK Department for International Development (DFID). Rapid evidence assessments. UK Government 2015. <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/rapid-evidence-assessments>.
- [43] Varker T, Forbes D, Dell L, Weston A, Merlin T, Hodson S, et al. Rapid evidence assessment: increasing the transparency of an emerging methodology. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice* 2015;21:1199–204. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jep.12405>.

- [44] Aronson JK, Heneghan C, Mahtani KR, Plüddemann A. A word about evidence: 'rapid reviews' or 'restricted reviews'? *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine* 2018;23:204–5. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2018-111025>.
- [45] Khan I, Hou F, Irfan M, Zakari A, Le HP. Does energy trilemma a driver of economic growth? The roles of energy use, population growth, and financial development. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2021;146:111157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111157>.
- [46] Plüddemann A, Aronson JK, Onakpoya I, Heneghan C, Mahtani KR. Redefining rapid reviews: a flexible framework for restricted systematic reviews. *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine* 2018;23:201–3. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2018-110990>.
- [47] Demeulenaere X. The use of automotive fleets to support the diffusion of Alternative Fuel Vehicles: A Rapid Evidence Assessment of barriers and decision mechanisms. *Research in Transportation Economics* 2019:100738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2019.100738>.